

TERM OF REFERENCE

IQTISHADUNA CONFERENCE: 1ST ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ISLAMIC ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT, BUSSINESS & ACCOUNTING

“The Role of Islamic Social Finance in Addressing Global Humanitarian Crises: Innovations, Challenges, and Collaboration”

Name of Conference

“IQTISHADUNA CONFERENCE: 1ST ANNUAL INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ISLAMIC ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT, BUSSINESS & ACCOUNTING”

Theme

“The Role of Islamic Social Finance in Addressing Global Humanitarian Crises: Innovations, Challenges, and Collaboration”

Sub Theme

1. Islamic Economics

- Sub-theme 1: Zakat, Waqf, Global Poverty Alleviation, Humanitarian Aid
- Sub-theme 2: Islamic Microfinance, Financial Inclusion, Post-Crisis Recovery
- Sub-theme 3: Islamic Finance, Blockchain, Transparency, Humanitarian Funding

2. Islamic Business

- Sub-theme 1: Sharia-Compliant Business, Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), Humanitarian Efforts
- Sub-theme 2: Halal Industry, Ethical Practices, Humanitarian Aid, Sustainable Development
- Sub-theme 3: Islamic Investment, Sustainable Development, Crisis Mitigation

3. Management

- Sub-theme 1: Islamic Leadership, Ethical Approaches, Crisis Management, Strategic Solutions
- Sub-theme 2: Islamic Governance, Organizational Efficiency, Humanitarian Emergencies
- Sub-theme 3: Risk Management, Islamic Financial Institutions, Global Crises

4. Islamic Accounting

- Sub-theme 1: Islamic Financial Reporting, Zakat and Waqf Accountability, Transparency in Humanitarian Aid
- Sub-theme 2: Auditing in Islamic Financial Institutions, Governance and Ethical Standards, Post-Crisis Financial Accountability
- Sub-theme 3: Islamic Social Finance, Blockchain in Islamic Accounting, Enhancing Efficiency in Crisis Response

**Note: Topics are not limited to those listed above. Submissions on other relevant topics in the fields of Economics, Management, Business, and Accounting are also welcome.*

Venue & Date

Shakti Hotel & FEBI UIN Sunan Gunung Djati - Bandung, Indonesia, November 21, 2024

2. Background

In recent years, the world has witnessed a significant rise in global humanitarian crises driven by various factors such as natural disasters, political conflicts, refugee crises, and pandemics. According to the United Nations, over 235 million people required humanitarian assistance in 2021, which highlights the scale of the challenge. The COVID-19 pandemic, in particular, has deepened economic disparities, pushing millions into extreme poverty and intensifying the need for effective humanitarian aid (United Nations, 2021). In response, Islamic social finance has emerged as a vital alternative, providing mechanisms rooted in principles of justice, wealth redistribution, and social responsibility. Instruments like zakat, infaq, sedekah, and waqf have historically been key in supporting the underprivileged. Zakat alone generates an estimated \$200 billion to \$1 trillion annually, which could be channeled into humanitarian efforts (World Zakat Forum, 2020). Additionally, Islamic microfinance and banking institutions are expanding financial inclusion, especially in developing countries, through interest-free loans and profit-sharing models (Obaidullah, 2008). Modern innovations, such as the use of blockchain technology, have also enhanced transparency and efficiency in distributing zakat and waqf funds, ensuring they reach the intended beneficiaries without delays (Hussain, 2020). The integration of Islamic social finance into global humanitarian responses, including collaborations with international organizations, shows great potential in addressing these crises more effectively. As discussed in the 1st Annual International Conference on Islamic Economics, Management & Business, leveraging Islamic finance with technology and international cooperation could significantly impact global efforts to alleviate suffering and support sustainable development (Karim, 2012).

Islamic social finance, including instruments like zakat, infaq, sedekah, and waqf, plays a critical role in addressing global humanitarian crises by providing immediate and sustainable support to vulnerable populations. Zakat, for example, is obligatory for Muslims and serves as a powerful mechanism to reduce poverty by redistributing wealth to those in need. Research shows that zakat funds could significantly contribute to poverty alleviation if effectively managed, with estimates suggesting an annual collection of \$200 billion to \$1 trillion globally (World Zakat Forum, 2020). In addition to zakat, waqf—an Islamic endowment—offers long-term solutions by funding sustainable development projects such as hospitals, schools, and public infrastructure, which are crucial in regions affected by conflict or disaster (Cizakca, 2011). Islamic microfinance and banking institutions further extend financial inclusion by providing interest-free loans and profit-sharing models that empower economically marginalized communities, particularly in developing countries (Obaidullah, 2008). These institutions operate on principles of equity and fairness, making them ideal for post-crisis recovery efforts. Moreover, businesses adhering to Islamic principles, often referred to as sharia-compliant businesses, can play a transformative role by committing to social responsibility, ethical investment, and sustainable practices that align with humanitarian goals (Karim, 2012). Together, these elements of Islamic finance create a robust framework for addressing both immediate and long-term challenges faced by communities in crisis. However, maximizing their potential requires strong governance, efficient management, and technological innovation. As highlighted in the 1st Annual International Conference on Islamic Economics, Management &

Business, integrating Islamic social finance with modern tools like blockchain can enhance transparency and accountability in fund distribution, ensuring aid reaches those who need it most (Hussain, 2020). Collaboration between Islamic financial institutions and international humanitarian organizations is essential for scaling up efforts to address global crises effectively.

Despite the immense potential of Islamic social finance and related institutions in addressing global humanitarian crises, several significant challenges hinder their effectiveness. One of the primary obstacles is the lack of standardized governance and regulatory frameworks across countries. While zakat, waqf, and other Islamic finance instruments are powerful tools for redistribution, their management often varies, leading to inefficiencies and a lack of transparency in fund allocation (World Bank, 2020). This issue is further compounded by limited public awareness about the proper mechanisms for collecting, distributing, and investing these funds, which hinders their potential to maximize impact on the ground. The absence of modern technological infrastructure within many Islamic finance institutions also impedes their ability to efficiently track and manage donations. In recent years, blockchain technology has emerged as a potential solution to enhance transparency and accountability in the distribution of zakat and waqf funds (Hussain, 2020). However, the adoption of such technologies has been slow due to regulatory concerns, lack of expertise, and initial implementation costs.

There is a critical need for more collaboration between Islamic financial institutions and global humanitarian organizations. While Islamic microfinance and sharia-compliant banking have made strides in promoting financial inclusion in developing countries, their impact remains limited by their localized nature and the fragmentation of the global Islamic financial system (Obaidullah, 2008). Effective partnerships between Islamic institutions and international entities like the United Nations or the World Bank could significantly enhance the scalability of Islamic finance solutions in response to global crises. Furthermore, challenges also arise in ensuring that Islamic social finance mechanisms align with modern humanitarian frameworks, such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), without compromising their core religious values. Addressing these challenges will require a concerted effort to innovate and modernize Islamic social finance, including the adoption of new technologies, the creation of standardized regulatory frameworks, and the fostering of international cooperation. As discussed in the 1st Annual International Conference on Islamic Economics, Management & Business, overcoming these barriers is essential for maximizing the impact of Islamic finance in global humanitarian efforts. By embracing innovation and building strong global networks, Islamic finance can realize its full potential in addressing crises, promoting financial inclusion, and contributing to sustainable development (Karim, 2012).

Objectives

*1. To Promote Scholarly Dialogue on **Islamic Social Finance** and Humanitarian Crises*

The primary objective of this conference is to create a platform for scholars, practitioners, and policymakers to engage in in-depth discussions on the role of Islamic social finance—such as zakat, waqf, and Islamic microfinance—in addressing global humanitarian crises. The conference aims to foster the exchange of ideas and innovative solutions to maximize the impact of Islamic financial mechanisms in alleviating poverty, supporting crisis response, and achieving sustainable development.

2. *To Encourage Collaboration between Islamic Financial Institutions and Global Humanitarian Organizations*

This conference seeks to promote collaboration between Islamic financial institutions, businesses, and international humanitarian organizations. By facilitating partnerships, the conference aims to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of Islamic financial solutions in global crisis management, ensuring a coordinated response to humanitarian emergencies.

3. *To Explore the Role of Technology in Enhancing Islamic Financial Transparency and Efficiency*

A key objective is to examine how modern technological innovations, such as blockchain, can be integrated into Islamic social finance to improve transparency, accountability, and the efficient distribution of funds. The conference will explore cutting-edge tools that can help Islamic financial institutions better serve communities affected by humanitarian crises.

4. *To Promote Financial Inclusion through Islamic Microfinance and Sharia-Compliant Businesses*

The conference also aims to highlight the potential of Islamic microfinance and sharia-compliant businesses in promoting financial inclusion, particularly in regions affected by poverty and crises. By fostering discussions on the role of ethical investment and inclusive business models, the conference seeks to identify practical solutions to empower marginalized communities.

5. *To Provide a Platform for Research Dissemination and Networking*

The conference serves as a forum for the dissemination of scholarly research and practical case studies. Participants will have the opportunity to present their research findings, network with peers from around the world, and collaborate on future research projects related to Islamic economics, management, and business in the context of global humanitarian efforts.

Target Audience

1. *Academics and Researchers in Islamic Economics, Management, Business, Accounting*

The conference is targeted at scholars, professors, and researchers specializing in Islamic economics, Islamic finance, Islamic management, and sharia-compliant business practices. It offers an opportunity for them to present their research, exchange ideas, and engage in academic discourse on how Islamic social finance can address global humanitarian crises.

2. *Islamic Financial Institutions and Practitioners*

The event is designed for professionals working in Islamic banks, Islamic microfinance institutions, and other Islamic financial organizations. They will gain insights into innovative strategies, tools, and collaborations to enhance the effectiveness of their financial instruments, especially in managing humanitarian emergencies and promoting financial inclusion.

3. *Policymakers and Government Officials*

Policymakers, regulators, and government representatives involved in Islamic finance, social welfare programs, and disaster management are key participants. The conference will provide them with knowledge on how to create conducive policies and frameworks that enable Islamic social finance to play a greater role in national and global humanitarian initiatives.

4. *Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and International Humanitarian Organizations*

Representatives from international humanitarian agencies, charities, and NGOs are encouraged to participate to explore partnerships with Islamic financial institutions. Their involvement will help build stronger collaborations in delivering efficient and transparent aid to communities affected by crises.

5. *Sharia-Compliant Businesses and Entrepreneurs*

The conference is also aimed at sharia-compliant businesses and entrepreneurs interested in incorporating social responsibility and ethical investment into their business models. Discussions will focus on how such businesses can contribute to humanitarian relief efforts and sustainable development.

6. *Graduate Students and Early-Career Researchers:*

Graduate students and young scholars specializing in Islamic economics, management, and business are invited to attend, offering them an opportunity to present their research, network with leading academics, and engage with practitioners. This will help nurture the next generation of leaders in Islamic finance and business.

Important Dates

- Paper Submission : September 27th – November 14th, 2024
- Acceptance Notification : 7 Days after Submission
- Conference Date : November 21st, 2024

Output Publication

- All Accepted Papers will be Published in International Proceeding
- Selected Papers will be Published in SINTA 3, 4, 5, 6 Accreditation Journal & National Journal

Speakers

- Prof. Dian Masyita, Ph.D, Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia (UIII).
- Hilmun Idzhar, Ph.D, Research Intitution, Islamic Development Bank Jeddah KSA.
- Bobby P Manullang, LAZ Dompot Dhuafa.
- Professor Mehmet Asutay, PhD. Professor of Middle Eastern and Islamic Political Economy & Finance, Durham University Business School.
- Dr. Arbaiah Abdul Razak, Deputy Director Graduate School of Management, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM- GSM).

FEE

- Offline Participant Fee : IDR. 250.000,-
- Online Participant Fee : IDR. 150.000,-
- Presenter Fee : IDR. 250.000,-/ Paper

Benefit for Participant

- Lunch & Twice Coffee Break
- Conference Merchandise Kit
- Printed Certificate
- International Network, Experience and Knowledge

Event Rundown

Time	Agenda		Details	
Nov,20 2024 19.30 – 21.00	Welcome Meeting with West Java Governor		All Participants and Organizer in West Java Governor Official House	
07:30 – 08:30	Registration and Welcome Coffee		Participants check-in, receive materials, and network	
08:30 – 08:40	Opening Ceremony		Welcome remarks by MC, Qur'an Recitation National Anthem, Hymne UIN SGD Bandung	
8:40 – 08:50	Opening Speech		Dean of Faculty of Islamic Economic and Bussiness, UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung	
08:50 – 09:20	Keynote 1: Topic Related with Speaker		Dr. Arbaiah Abdul Razak, Deputy Director Graduate School of Management, International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM- GSM).	
09:20 – 09:50	Keynote 2: Topic Related with Speaker		Bobby P Manullang, LAZ Dompot Dhuafa.	
09:50 – 10:20	Keynote 3: Topic Related with Speaker		Prof. Dian Masyita, Ph.D, Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Universitas Islam Internasional Indonesia (UIII).	
10:20 – 10:50	Keynote 4: Topic Related with Speaker		Hilmun Idzhar, Ph.D, Research Intitution, Islamic Development Bank Jeddah KSA.	
10:50 – 11:20	Keynote 5: Topic Related with Speaker		Professor Mehmet Asutay, PhD. Professor of Middle Eastern and Islamic Political Economy & Finance, Durham University Business School	
11:20 – 12:00	Plenary Session: Innovations in Islamic Finance for Humanitarian Crises		Panel discussion on Islamic finance, blockchain, and partnerships in crisis management	
12:00 – 13:00	Break for Lunch, Sholat, and Networking		Time for lunch, prayer, and networking	
Time	Room 1: Islamic Economics	Room 2: Islamic Business	Room 3: Management	Room 4: Accounting
13:00 – 15:30	Paralel Sesion	Paralel Sesion	Paralel Sesion	Paralel Sesion

15.30 - 16.00	Coffee Break and Sholat			
16.00 - 17.00	Room 1: Islamic Economics	Room 2: Islamic Business	Room 3: Management	Room 4: Accounting
17.00	Closing Remarks and Awards Ceremony			Conference summary and best paper/poster awards

Organizing Committee Structure

1. Steering Committee (Komite Pengarah)

- Chairperson: Prof. Dr. H. Dudang Gojali, M.Ag, Dean of Faculty Islamic Economics and Bussiness

Responsible for overseeing the entire conference, ensuring alignment with objectives, and making final decisions on key issues.

- Advisory Board:
 - Dr. Muhammad Zaky, SE., M.Si. CHRA, Vice Dean of Faculty Islamic Economics and Bussiness
 - Dr. H. Kadar Nurjaman, SE., MM., CHRA, Vice Dean of Faculty Islamic Economics and Bussiness

Provides guidance and strategic direction for the conference. Typically consists of senior academics and professionals in Islamic economics and business.

2. Organizing Committee

- Conference Coordinator: Dr. Iwan Setiawan, S.Ag., M.Pd., M.E.Sy CIIQA, CIELP
Manages day-to-day operations, coordinates between various committees, and ensures smooth execution of all activities.
- Secretary : Adi Suharyo, S.HI, M.Ag., M.Kom
Vice Secretary : Avid Leonardo Sari, S.ST, M.PS, Sp., MM
Member : Akbar Riskal Amani, SE., M.S.M
Aldriantara Sofyan

Handles official correspondence, manages documentation, and ensures proper communication between all committee members.

- Treasurer: Ade Ponirah, SE., M.E

Manages the conference budget, oversees financial transactions, and ensures transparency in financial reporting.

3. Program Committee

Program Chair: Akbar Riskal Amani, SE., M.S.M, Annisa Nur Salam, SE., M.E , Dr. M. Sandi Martha, SE., MM

- Responsible for designing and overseeing the scientific content of the conference, including keynote sessions, plenary panels, and parallel sessions.
- Scientific Committee:
 - Prof. Dr. Lilis Sulastrri, MM
 - Dr. Dadang Husen Sobana, M.Ag
 - Dr. Evi Sopiah, M.Ag
 - Mia Lasmi Wardiyah, SP., M.Ag
 - Dr. Iman Supratman, M.Ag
 - Vemi Suci Asih, M.E.Sy
 - Annisa Ilmia, M.E
 - Fitri Dzikrayah, M.E.Sy
 - Budi Budiman, M.Ag., M.Si

Reviews submitted abstracts and papers, ensuring academic quality, and works closely with the Program Chair to develop the conference agenda.

- Session Moderators:
 - Suteja Wiradanakusumah, S.ST. Par., M.E
 - Gina Sakinah, M.E.Sy
 - Agus Joharudin, M.Int, Buss
 - Dr. Muhammad Al Mighwar, M.Ag

Moderates discussions during the keynote and parallel sessions, ensuring smooth and timely proceedings.

4. Logistics Committee

- Logistics Manager:
 - Adi Suharyo, S.HI, M.Ag., M.Kom
 - Ahmad Imanudin, S.Hum
 - All Faculty Staff of Islamic Economics and Bussiness (Include OB and Security)

Oversees the venue setup, audiovisual equipment, transportation arrangements, and accommodation for attendees.

- IT and Technical Support Team: PTIPD UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung

Manages technical aspects of the conference, including online platforms, presentation technology, and troubleshooting technical issues during the event.

5. Registration and Hospitality Committee

- Registration Coordinator:
 - Ade Ponirah, SE., M.E
 - Elsa Yulandri, SE., M.E

Daraini Anwar, S.Ikom
Neli Yuliyani, S.Akun

Handles participant registration, manages conference materials, and oversees the registration desk during the event.

- Hospitality Team:
 - Husni Abdillah, S.Sos
 - Dimas Hardyansyah, S.Akun
 - Rifki M Fauzi, SE
 - Maolana Ependi, SE
 - Yus Yulian, S.Sos
 - Rismawati, S.Pd
 - Fulki Fadhludin, SH
 - Abdul Haris Citra Atmaja, S.Ag

Welcomes participants, manages accommodation, and ensures smooth coordination of travel and local logistics for speakers and international guests.

6. Public Relations and Marketing Committee

- PR and Media Coordinator:
 - Nabiela Rizky Alifa, S.KPM., MM
 - Reja Fauzi Nazar, SH., MH

Manages conference promotion through social media, press releases, and official announcements, and coordinates media coverage.

7. Sponsorship and Fundraising Committee

- Sponsorship Coordinator:
 - Dr. H. Ateng Kusnandar, SH., MM
 - Gina Sakinah, SE.Sy., ME
 - Awang Dodi Kardeli, S.Pd., M.MPd

Secures sponsors and partnerships for the conference, manages sponsor relations, and ensures sponsor deliverables are met.

Identifies potential donors and partners, drafts proposals, and works to secure financial support for the conference.

- Volunteer Coordinator: Manages volunteers who assist in running the conference smoothly.
 - M. Nadhir Mu'ammam, S.ThI., M.Ud
 - Babay Suhaemi, M.Ag
 - Zia Sidqurrahman, M.Pd
 - KPM & GPM FEBI UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung
 - DEMA & SEMA
 - HMJ Manajemen, Akuntansi Syariah, Ekonomi Syariah, Manajemen Keuangan Syariah

Conclusion

The 1st Annual International Conference on Islamic Economics, Management & Business presents a unique opportunity to explore the significant role of Islamic social finance in addressing global humanitarian crises. Through discussions on topics such as zakat, waqf, Islamic microfinance, and the contribution of sharia-compliant businesses, this conference seeks to highlight innovative approaches to poverty alleviation, crisis recovery, and sustainable development. With a focus on collaboration between academic scholars, practitioners, policymakers, and international humanitarian organizations, the event will foster interdisciplinary dialogue and practical solutions to global challenges. The inclusion of cutting-edge technologies, such as blockchain for financial transparency, further demonstrates the potential of Islamic finance in modern crisis management. By gathering experts and stakeholders from various sectors, the conference aims to promote knowledge exchange, establish partnerships, and contribute to the advancement of Islamic economic and business practices. The outcomes of this conference are expected to drive future research, inform policy decisions, and enhance the impact of Islamic social finance on both national and international levels. This conference marks an important step forward in recognizing the transformative potential of Islamic financial instruments and management strategies in the global context. The collective efforts and insights shared during this event will contribute to the realization of a more inclusive and equitable financial system that addresses the pressing needs of communities affected by crises.

Reference

1. Cizakca, M. (2011). Waqf in history and its implications for modern Islamic economies. *Islamic Economic Studies*.
2. Hussain, M. (2020). Blockchain and the future of Islamic finance. *Journal of Islamic Finance*.
3. Karim, N. (2012). Islamic Banking and Microfinance in Bangladesh. *Islamic Finance News*.
4. Obaidullah, M. (2008). *Islamic Microfinance for Poverty Alleviation*.
5. United Nations. (2021). *Global Humanitarian Overview 2021*.
6. World Bank. (2020). *Islamic Finance: Opportunities, Challenges, and the Road to SDGs*.
7. World Zakat Forum. (2020). *Global Zakat Report*.